

iJEResearch

International Journal of Education and Research

Vol-1, Number 1, March- 2023 | Peer-Reviewed Journal

ISSN 2764-9733 | ijerresearch.org

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8403544

PSYCHO-PEDAGOGICAL INTERVENTION: STUDY DEVELOPED AT THE FRANCISCAN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTE OF PAÇO DO LUMIAR, MA

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ABSTRACT

This present article aims to present the case study carried out at the Instituto de Ensino Superior Franciscano (IESF, private college) and its approaches to the Psychopedagogy and continuing education relevance for psycho-pedagogues participating in the Psychopedagogical Intervention Social Project (ProSIPp), developed in the institution. This study sought to answer the following question: Does ProSIPp allow other perspective use to define the psycho-pedagogue professional praxis? Does the psycho-pedagogue strengthen its intervention practices through participation in the project? The proposed objective was to inquire about the ProSIPp influence in the psychopedagogists continuing education process, through the theories and practices acquired arising from psychopedagogical interventions was seen as a professional profile development. All psycho-pedagogues who participated in the project from 2017 to 2019, making a total of 24 and the selected sample was 50%, which corresponds to 12 psycho-pedagogues who were corresponded by the research universe. It was possible to perceive the ProSIPp social role importance by its results, which contributed satisfactorily to the difficulties minimization related to learning and also provided a new vision of the psychopedagogist profession, which needs to be improved regarding the knowledge in the area advances to assist those who need help in building learning better.

Keywords: Psychopedagogy. Psychopedagogical service. ProSIPp. IESF.

INTRODUCTION

Psychopedagogy is an area of knowledge that deals with the human learning process, having the human being itself as the object of study, in the apprehension of reality and the construction of knowledge. Psychopedagogy studies the teaching-learning process and its difficulties, mainly related to pedagogical practice, involving meeting individual and group needs, learning, school failure and appropriation of knowledge by the subject.

Concerned with the diversity of courses, the Brazilian Association of Psychopedagogy (ABPp) has been vehemently discussing topics related to the training of this professional, such as the identity of the Psychopedagogue, the recognition of activities, the legitimacy of the social action of Psychopedagogy, among others.

Deepening the understanding of Psychopedagogy has become relevant as one also seeks to understand the relevance of continuing education for professionals in the area. Thus, the following proposal arose: "FROM TRAINING TO PSYCHO-PEDAGOGICAL INTERVENTION: a study based on the Social Project of Psycho-pedagogical Intervention (ProSIPp) developed at the Franciscan Higher Education Institute in Paço do Lumiar-MA". The Instituto de Ensino Superior Franciscano (IESF) is located in Maiobão, in the municipality of Paço do Lumiar-MA, which for seven years has been gradually undergoing a reformulation of its curriculum design, trying to follow the guidelines set out in the Education Guidelines for Psychopedagogues in Brazil, from the moment in which the HEI is concerned with the training of its students, when it offers supervised practice in its course structure, called Supervised Internship, which includes a psycho-pedagogical evaluation and the desire to detail about the constitution and development of the Social Project for Psychopedagogical Intervention (ProSIPp), whose focus is to contribute to the post-training of newly graduated students from the IES Psychopedagogy Course, thus extending psycho-pedagogical intervention to the surrounding community, children and adolescents from public schools or private, previously evaluated and diagnosed in the internship, with learning difficulties.

To carry out the study and carry out the proposal

contained in this project, it will be necessary to use two methodological mechanisms: Bibliographic Research and the Case Study. To answer the question proposed in the project, the following procedures will be followed: analysis of the ProSIPp documentation and study of the actions developed by the ProSIPp. The research universe corresponds to all psycho-pedagogues who participated in the project from 2017 to 2019, making a total of 24. And the selected sample will be 50%, which corresponds to 12 psycho-pedagogues.

The research aims to deepen the understanding of Psychopedagogy, making it essential, as it also seeks to understand the relevance of continuing education for newly formed psychopedagogues. The general objective of the research was to inquire about the influence of ProSIPp in the psychopedagogue's continuing education process and to develop a professional profile based on the acquisition of theories and practices resulting from psycho-pedagogical interventions.

The research interest is reinforced by the desire to present the ProSIPp, developed at the Instituto de Ensino Superior Franciscano (IESF), considering its multiple relevance in the fields of psycho-pedagogical assistance, in the continuing education of educational psychologists and social responsibility.

APPROACH TO PSYCHO PEDAGOGY

When mentioning the advent of Psychopedagogy, we bring the writings of Pain (2012), which clarifies that even today, one of the difficult problems for Pedagogy is the relationship between the construction of knowledge by the individual and the constitution of the subject through knowledge. The author emphasizes that Pedagogy, at the time, did not take into account the individual and his history, his destiny, something that differentiated him from other individuals, that is, his uniqueness. In Rubinstein's writings (2012, p. 15), she emphasizes the following:

Long before talking about Psychopedagogy, Special Education, Therapeutic Pedagogy, and Re-education, there was already news of educational experiences aimed at specific situations that involved limitations in the learning

of an organic or even social nature.

The author continues by stating that the activities were developed, sometimes intuitively, by educators who had idealism and utopia as flags. In this way, from humanists, romantics and idealists, specialized educators became re-educators, specialists in the treatment of learning problems. One of the treatment objectives was to prove the efficiency of tests applied to schoolchildren within a given testing period.

Given the procedures adopted, the words of Rubinstein (2012) undoubtedly confirm this is a caricatured and synthetic view of re-education. And, he continues “probably, many more sensitive re-educators, intuitively, did not limit themselves to administering tests and proposing series of exercises, focusing their attention on the subject. For her, the positive results of the tests occurred due to the insistence and belief in the possibilities for human beings to change.

Such insistence and belief, originated from dreamers, idealists, and non-conformists, who have always existed in all areas, says Rubinstein (2012). As proof, it brings, among others, the figure of Ann Sullivan, who, out of idealism, was willing to bring about changes where they were little expected. That is, they reached out to people who, for different reasons, were socially marginal. Therefore, the author points out that it is possible to believe that re-educators, due to their profile of dreamers, had a great capacity to deal with the limits and frustrations arising from the dramatic conditions they faced.

Based on Rubinstein’s statement (2012) about idealistic educators and their attitudes towards the care provided to socially disadvantaged children, and that this attitude gave rise to the positive results of the applied tests, consequently, transformations emerged. The changes, or rather the transformations, began with the arrival of the 20th century, even with therapeutic interventions in the medical/pedagogical approach, with a view to re-education, focusing on a certain clientele. In this case, re-education centres were built for child offenders. This time, it appears in the literary context, not only in Europe, but the United

States, both with the following history: “In the United States and Europe, the number of private schools and individualized teaching for children considered to be slow learners is growing”. (BOSSA, 2011, p. 59).

For Rubinstein (2012) re-education could become Psychopedagogy when it embraced and built a broader ideological platform on the concept of learning, using a multidisciplinary view. For the author, in Psychopedagogy, the fundamental thing is to know and understand the learning process, to understand the learning difficulty from it. According to her, this assumption contributes to modifying the understanding of the etiology of learning difficulties, as well as the modality of intervention.

In his exposition, Rubinstein presents the definition of learning elaborated by Dabas (1998), for judging it to be quite clear. As he goes on to mention that learning is the process by which a subject, in his interaction with the environment, incorporates the information offered by this environment, according to his needs and interests”. (DABAS, 1998 apud RUBINSTEIN, 2012).

In this sense, he goes on to state that this happens: He elaborates this information through his psychic structure, constituted by the social interplay, the dynamics of the unconscious and the cognitive dynamics, modifying his behaviour to accept new proposals and carry out unprecedented transformations in the environment that surrounds him. (DABAS, 1998 apud RUBINSTEIN, 2012).

Following the historical context, let’s see what is the definition of the object of study of psychopedagogy according to some theorists:

The objective of the psycho-pedagogical treatment is the disappearance of the symptom and the possibility for the subject to learn normally in better conditions, emphasizing the relationship that he may have with learning, that is, that the subject is the agent of his learning and that he appropriates of knowledge. (PAIN

apud ARAGÃO, 2010, p. 21).

Scoz and Barone (apud ARAGÃO, 2010, p. 22) define: “[...] psychopedagogy as an area that studies and deals with the learning process and its difficulties and that in a professional action, it must encompass several fields of knowledge, integrating and systematizing them”.

These different meanings related to psychopedagogy tell us about a process that is being structured, and whose identity is maturing. As Macedo states (apud ARAGÃO, 2010, p. 34), “[...] psychopedagogy is a (new) area of professional activity that seeks an identity that requires training at an interdisciplinary level”. Currently, even as an area of knowledge, Psychopedagogy deals with the human learning process, having the human being itself as the object of study, in the apprehension of reality and the construction of knowledge.

Psychopedagogy studies the teaching-learning process and its difficulties, mainly related to pedagogical practice, envisioning how the subject relates affectively, cognitively, pedagogically and socially with learning. Respecting this subject's need for care in individual and group circumstances, paying attention to their learning modality, to minimize or solve the difficulty of learning. This difficulty, which may be related to internal and/or external factors to the learner, is sometimes addressed to school failure.

According to Escott (2004 apud ARAGÃO, 2010), in the psycho-pedagogical diagnosis, it is necessary to identify, in the subject's development and in the relationship with his family and social groups in which he lives, the meaning of non-learning. Thus, Clinical Psychopedagogy starts from the subject's personal history, seeking to identify their learning modality and understand the message of other subjects involved in this process, be it the family or the school, seeking, implicitly or not, the causes of not learning. Emphasizing the clinical approach, the author stresses that it goes through an intense process of investigation into the intriguing factors of the subject's non-learning, which is called psycho-pedagogical diagnosis.

Linked to Bossa's thinking on psycho-pedagogical diagnosis, for Weiss (2016) what is important in this process is the perception of the individual way each person learns and produces. In pursuit of understanding learning difficulties and the factors that can lead to school failure.

Still on the clinical approach, Bossa (2011) points out that clinical work takes place through the relationship between personal history and the learning modality. It is of fundamental importance that the psycho-pedagogue professional can identify how the subject is constituted, what transformations he has undergone throughout the different stages of life, what structures and concepts he has built and how he relates to knowledge. Therefore, it becomes necessary for the clinical psycho-pedagogue to assume it as a duty, not only to seek to understand why the subject has a certain learning difficulty, but how he can learn and how this learning process will take place. This understanding will begin in the diagnostic process, as latent desires for learning are released by the learning subject, thus allowing for this understanding.

As pointed out above, the diagnosis is the starting point for psycho-pedagogical investigation. However, it is worth mentioning that, in the sense of evolution, affirmation and support of Psychopedagogy, the Techniques of Psychopedagogical Diagnosis have been improving, opening space for reflection to psychopedagogues, on the procedures adopted in their modality of performance.

Facing this manifestation, Rubinstein (2001, p. 24) emphasizes: If, in the re-education approach, what is in evidence as an object of research is the failure as a deviation, in the dynamic psychopedagogy approach, it is intended to understand the failures within the perspective of the subject of learning, that is, understanding and raising possible hypotheses for this deviation or this unsatisfactory relationship with knowledge and knowledge.

When thinking about Psychopedagogy in the Brazilian context, it is admitted that in Brazil, there

are two paths to follow, in the search for training in Psychopedagogy, at the undergraduate and Post-Graduate *Latu Sensu* levels. Regarding the latter, in the modalities: face-to-face, blended and distance learning, with different workloads. The *Latu Sensu* format stands out in terms of offering more courses, for this reason, specialization must be considered as a starting point in the training of psycho-pedagogues in Brazil.

Continuing the thought above, Serrano (2001 apud PERES, 2014) among other words informs that training in Psychopedagogy is taking place, in general, in *Latu Sensu* Postgraduate courses, linked to educational institutions that meet the requirements established by the National Board of Education.

About the formation of psychopedagogues in Brazil, it has always been a concern of those who headed Psychopedagogy to establish itself in Brazil, since the foundation of the State Association of Psychopedagogues of São Paulo (AEP), whose objective was to work on the professional profile, the field of performance and the formation of the psychopedagogue. (BARONE, 2020). Even before the AEP, there were already meetings between the members of the group that constituted it. In the meetings they discussed, and each time they advanced the identity, role and field of action of the psycho-pedagogue. Between the lines, words from Noffs (2003, p. 58). As for the time, Rubinstein (2020, p. 27) reinforces: "Continuing education, deepening and interest in innovations in the educational and psycho-pedagogical field were our priorities". Rubinstein (2020) emphasizes that at the time of the AEP, young psychopedagogues used to work together, despite the commissions. Thus, he recalls: "At each Board meeting we asked ourselves: What does a psychopedagogue do? What is Psychopedagogy? The reduced steering group, composed of a maximum of 20 professional colleagues from different backgrounds and interests, shared knowledge". (RUBINSTEIN, 2020, p. 27).

GETTING TO KNOW THE SOCIAL PROJECT OF PSYCHO-PEDAGOGICAL INTERVENTION (PROSIPp)

The research institution of this study is the Instituto de Ensino Superior Franciscano (IESF) located in the municipality of Paço do Lumiar/MA, which maintains the Integrated Center for Pedagogical and Psychopedagogical Monitoring and Management (NIGApp), which is a psychopedagogical support service and psychological to academics and professors of undergraduate and graduate courses at the HEI, in face-to-face and distance learning modalities. The NIGApp is a space that brings together different services that are available to teachers/tutors and students of *Latu Sensu* Undergraduate and Postgraduate Courses, as well as monitors and supports the Course Coordination, Distance Learning Coordination and the Evaluation Commission, in monitoring all actions to support the needs identified throughout the process, aiming at improving individual and/or collective performance. The Social Project of Psychopedagogical Intervention (ProSIPp), will also contribute to the level of improvement of the practice in psychopedagogy for students coming from the Psychopedagogy Course, thus, ProSIPp starts its activities in 2016, given a year of observation that generated many concerns in the researcher. Concerns arose around the significant demand of children and adolescents participating in the internship with hypotheses of difficulties in learning to read, write and calculate. As well as meeting the aspirations of students completing the aforementioned course, extending their studies and continuing their practical work in Psychopedagogy.

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results obtained in the case study based on the analysis of the information contained in the data collection instrument. When asked about their knowledge of ProSIPp, the sample was unanimous in responding that it had access to the project during the supervised internship, in the Specialization Course in Psychopedagogy at IESF. The project intends to cover the following target audience: "Learners evaluated in the Supervised Internship in Psychopedagogy, as well as their families, psychopedagogues and volunteer monitors and Internship Supervisor". (IESF, 2016, p. 1).

I got to know ProSIPp during the internship discipline of the Specialization Course in Institutional and Clinical Psychopedagogy, offered by the Instituto de Ensino Superior Franciscano-IESF. At first, through the teacher's exposition about this project and later, during the development of the internship in the same place where the project was developed. In this space, there was a panel with images and small texts that validated the activities developed in ProSIPp. (INTERVIEWEE).

The above mention goes against the data obtained since the project is disclosed to the students of the postgraduate course in Psychopedagogy of the IESF, at the time of the supervised internship, which constitutes the last three disciplines of the course, it is also disclosed in the institution's digital media so that the announcement can reach the knowledge of the graduates of the said course. The question below deals with the description of how that phase was, as ProSIPp has two distinct phases: a theoretical phase and a practical phase.

ProSIPp in 2019 returned with a new theoretical and methodological perspective. The project aimed to work on reading and writing in a dialogical perspective, through textual genres. To this end, the first step was to re-elaborate the ProSIPp work project based on the study of theorists who were aligned with this proposal. In the second moment, the training meetings were designed based on this reference and with this reference. Therefore, reading the selected material was a key factor in this process, not just any reading, but a reflective reading that resulted in records of the texts read. (INTERVIEWEE).

The study phase of the project was described by the psycho-pedagogues as an important phase because it brought explanations about the methodologies used by the psycho-pedagogue,

at the time that dialogue circles and exchange of experience about what was read were held. In this calm process and mediated by the ProSIPp coordinator, who always coordinated the discussions, the group's intellectual enrichment happened. The study addressed several theorists who in the future would help in the intervention process.

The theoretical phase comprises every part of the study that is developed by the project members, through meetings, studies of specialized texts and deepening on renowned theorists. This phase allows reflection and study with emphasis on the perception of the object of psychopedagogy and its manifestation. The study on the methodologies and instruments of psychopedagogy is also included, aiming at future intervention.

About the execution, the project started with a planning meeting with the project coordination, there was a welcome for the Psychopedagogues who worked on the project.

Regarding the development of the project, the following actions can be mentioned:

[...] the dossier of each learner is read, received by the students and family members responsible, then the intervention sessions begin with specific materials and instruments according to the needs of the students, evaluation of the practice and adjustments in the planning when necessary and they give back to families. (INTERVIEWEE).

Continuing with the reports, one of the interviewees reported that the project was carried out on Tuesdays, by two volunteer psychopedagogues, which took place from 6:30 pm to 7:50 pm (1 hour and 20 minutes duration) for the service time. There were 20 meetings interspersed with group studies.

This phase was identified as very productive and challenging, as there were 2 groups of customers, each with its specificities. The first moment was the contact with the families and clients, in which dynamics were carried out with them to have

the first observations, from there, sessions were carried out based on the diagnosis of each one, being based on the project proposal on Genders Literary, in which fairy tales, fables, riddles, letters, etc. were worked on... Following a didactic sequence in each session about the genres worked on.

The project was carried out in pairs, and initially, we found out about the complaints brought by the families/school, through the files/files of each client, so that we could carry out an assertive intervention in each identified learning difficulty. We sought to find out whether, during the development of the project, there was a need to use classic instruments of Psychopedagogy learned during the training in Psychopedagogy, and as answers projective tests, operative tests, drawings, various games, toys, and games were cited according to the age range and difficulty observed by each client. Piagetian proofs and the projective techniques used were recurrent in the intervention process to confirm or disqualify previous readings made in the process. For example, the projective technique A Planta da Casa was used to confirm hypotheses raised during the internship evaluation service.

The intervention took place through textual genres, games, reading workshops, production of stories (autobiography, short stories, poems) through posters and others, activities in the toy library, and activities that involved feelings (self-esteem) with the use of plaques with positive messages and emojis. (INTERVIEWEE).

It was emphasized that psycho-pedagogical games were made, activities were organized that favoured the learning of learners according to needs, in addition, medical records were organized to develop the intervention plan. The next question was whether, during participation in the project, there was the elaboration of any instrument(s) based on the diagnosed reality and which ones, where it was informed that instruments aimed at literacy were used, such as pairing, rhyme, reading pyramid, syllable stripes among others. Also cited were:

group diary, group life book, conversation wheel and others.

On the influence of ProSIPp in strengthening the professional identity of the Psychopedagogue, in addition to seeking if there was understanding about the psycho-pedagogical work.

Regarding the question: According to your perception, how does ProSIPp influence the strengthening of the Psychopedagogue's professional identity? There is the following analysis: The ProSIPp influences the identity of the psycho pedagogue when it allows the newly graduated in psychopedagogy the opportunity to continue with assistance and studies, as this way we acquire more experience about the psycho-pedagogical practice. The ProSIPp through the studies provided the perception that there are factors that interfere with the student's learning. The ProSIPp enables psycho-pedagogues to experience psycho-pedagogical practice supervised by more experienced Psychopedagogues and guided by a theoretical-methodological framework in a space of action with real demands, something scarce in the Metropolitan Region of São Luís. This perspective of training enables psycho-pedagogues to experience training which makes them safer in their performance.

It enabled the exercise of work activity more autonomously and safely, allowing doubts to be resolved and professional identity strengthened mainly through observation and the search for knowledge, through scientific research. The project provided the Psychopedagogue with first contact with his role, thus searching for his identity according to his performance/practice.

The answers allow us to state how much the ProSIPp had a positive impact on the training and professional identity of the psycho-pedagogues who participated in the project, the following report can be presented:

The importance of having a holistic view of the subject; The importance of listening to all subjects who are involved with the development of the learning subject; Organization, planning, commitment and study are essential;

you can learn from everyone, always. The psycho-pedagogical intervention is something serious, it can harm the development of the learner if it is not taken seriously by the professionals responsible for promoting learning. (INTERVIEWEE).

Other aspects were mentioned as a guarantee to the community of professional subsidies in the psycho-pedagogical field that made possible the change in the educational scenario, by minimizing learning difficulties through psycho-pedagogical assistance.

The physical space, resources and theoretical support ensured a cohesive work, with rich learning possibilities for the psychopedagogue's personal and professional life. It is possible here to highlight other aspects considered relevant: it prepares one to analyze and understand the cause of learning difficulty, it enables one to reflect on what instruments one can use to overcome the difficulty, it develops creativity and an innovative spirit, it encourages research and looking for theorists who advise which paths to follow, sensitizes to seek activities that promote the self-esteem of clients and generating new knowledge. This analysis made it possible to verify that the project provided training and learning opportunities for new Psychopedagogues, as well as contributed to the intervention process of low-income people in the community and fulfilled the objective of seeking to give a positive response to the client in the face of the problems that are facing related to their children's learning.

About the professional profile, based on participation in the project: The results of the research demonstrate that there was a learning experience in terms of taking better care of the psycho-pedagogical work, investing in training and resources, being more cautious, exercising better listening and also in learning about looking at the subject instead of their conflicting situations.

There was a re-dimensioning of the professional profile, because before, some interviewees considered their knowledge in the field of

psychopedagogy incipient, and now they are stronger professionals able to extend a hand to a child, or an adolescent, who will investigate what is affecting their learning and will find alternatives to overcome these difficulties. But I know I still have a lot to learn.

[...] Even with experience in other spaces, I still didn't feel safe acting. My biggest concern has always been the lack of a theoretical framework and the mix of theorists that many psycho-pedagogues used to support their work. Through the project, I was able to study theorists who provided answers to my concerns and challenges experienced in psycho-pedagogical work. (INTERVIEWEE).

It was possible to perceive the importance of the social role, to contribute satisfactorily to the minimization of difficulties related to learning. There was a new vision of the psycho-pedagogue profession, which needs to be up to date with knowledge and advances in the area to better assist those who need help in the construction of learning. Participation in the project was identified as an excellent experience, which opened the horizons of what is needed to develop a work of excellence in the area.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Thinking about the strengthening of Psychopedagogy through continuing education, I suggest that HEIs with specialization courses in Psychopedagogy offer former students the possibility of insertion in an extension project, as a proposal for continuing education. Where the former student, now a professional, finds in this possibility, conditions to outline his practice, deepening his knowledge, and through the use of other lenses, encourage himself to use new resources and/or instruments in psycho-pedagogical intervention.

Therefore, the training proposal envisages the maintenance of a teaching and learning sequence, relating theory to practice, favouring the encouragement of recent graduates to face the job market.

Based on fifteen years of professional experience in Psychopedagogy, for nine years Psychopedagogy has been working in the social dimension, when it seeks knowledge, through socio-educational action, believing that learning takes place in the institution, whether educational or family, articulating the accumulated experience with what is present.

From this perspective, the Social Project of Psychopedagogical Intervention (ProSIPp) is born, which is developed within an HEI, serving schools, families, and students, reminiscent of a psycho-pedagogical evaluation process, which includes the practice of the Specialization Course of the Institute of Higher Education Franciscano (IESF), located in the municipality of Paço do Lumiar-MA.

Given the study's exposition, it is believed that the training structure of the HEI in question meets the principles of the ABPP, regarding the training and post-training of the psychopedagogue in Brazil, when the IESF, guarantees in its staff, a psychopedagogical professional, to meet and pay attention to the evolutionary needs of their course and consequently accompany the students in the disciplines of Psychopedagogical Practice, called Supervised Internship, which takes place in a proper, equipped and healthy environment.

The institution that hosted the research was the Instituto de Ensino Superior Franciscano (IESF), and one of the criteria was due to the concern with the provision of continuing education to its former students, through extension projects, which allow practical tests that favour the intertwine between theory and practice to strengthen future performance as a professional. After explaining the same exposed in this study and the conclusions, we present here the recommendations for ProSIPp to continue its educational and social contribution, collaborating with the development of the region it serves. It is important to point out that the project, as it has been developed to date, had a positive impact on the educational context of many children and on strengthening the professional identity of the educational psychologists who participated in the

project. The analysis made through the collected data shows that the project is on the right path. In this way, the recommendations mentioned below, aim to contribute to the expansion of the project, leaving the IESF with the study and viability of them.

That the institution can expand the ProSIPp, guaranteeing its growth through: increasing the number of vacancies proposed in the Notices, considering that the demand and need for psychopedagogical assistance is real and the NIGAPP has a growing demand, ideally that more vacancies with a view to meeting the demand specified above; celebration of agreements with educational institutions, these agreements seek partnerships, thinking in the context of basic education and that the Project can serve more children; expansion of the physical space, the intention is to maximize the service by having a wider and more adequate space; creation of the "ProSIPp na Escola" project, as a result of the pandemic, people began to think about a way to implement the project, where children did not need to go to the IESF to be assisted; that the IESF can create a repository of knowledge through the productions generated from it, such as reports, reports and articles; that NIGAPP institute an annual event with ProSIPp productions.

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